

Quinazolones. Part IV. Synthesis of Some Allyloxy Quinazolones

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Synthesis of 7-allyloxy-6-methoxy- (XII), 7-allyloxy-8-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H) one (XI) and 7-allyloxy-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XIII) from the respective benzo-xazines is described and the effect of the substituents in the benzene ring discussed.

Allyloxy quinazolones having one of the ortho positions blocked have been considered to be the key-intermediates for the synthesis of furoquinazolones^{1,2}. The present communication deals with the synthesis of some such allyloxy quinazolones starting from ortho-aminobenzoic acids *via* benzoxazines.

4-Allyloxy-5-methoxy-6-aminobenzoic acid (I)² and 4-allyloxy-3-methoxy-6-aminobenzoic acid (II)¹ when refluxed with a minimum volume of acetic anhydride gave the respective benzoxazin-4-ones VI and VII only on cooling or when the solvent in excess was distilled under reduced pressure and subsequently washed with dry ether. If the reaction mixture was poured in crushed ice, the acetamidobenzoic acids III and IV were the sole products. The benzoxazine derivative VIII was, however, obtained differently by the action of benzoyl chloride in dry pyridine on I and was found to be identical with that obtained by the action of acetic anhydride on 4-allyloxy-5-methoxy-6-benzamodibenzoic acid (V) according to the literature procedure³. Unlike the simple 2-methylbenzoxazines, VI and VII do not hydrolyse with atmospheric moisture and can be preserved for days together;

I : R = OMe ;	R ₁ = H ;	R ₂ = NH ₂
II : R = H ;	R ₁ = OMe ;	R ₂ = NH ₂
III : R = OMe ;	R ₁ = H	R ₂ = NHAc
IV : R = H ;	R ₁ = OMe ;	R ₂ = NHAc
V : R = OMe ₁	R ₁ = H ;	R ₂ = NHCOPh

1. S. K. P. Sinha and D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 31.

2. V. Shrivastava and D. N. Chaudhury, *ibid.*, 1969, **46**, 651.

but when kept overnight in contact with water they get converted to the respective acetamido acids III and IV.

fig. 2

VI : R = OMe;	R ₁ = O allyl;	R ₂ = H;	R ₃ = Me
VII : R = H;	R ₁ = O allyl;	R ₂ = OMe;	R ₃ = Me
VIII : R = OMe;	R ₁ = O allyl;	R ₂ = H;	R ₃ = Ph
IX : R = H;	R ₁ = OMe;	R ₂ = OAc;	R ₃ = Me
X : R = H;	R ₁ = OMe;	R ₂ = PhCOO;	R ₃ = Ph

The benzoxazines VI, VII and VIII were readily converted to the 4-quinazolones XI, XII and XIII respectively when boiled with aniline in toluene for 4 hrs. Like isomeric 6-allyloxy-7-methoxyquinazolin-4(3H)-ones^{3,4} the 7-allyloxy-6-methoxyquinazolones XII and XIV on Claisen rearrangement and subsequent treatment with excess ethereal diazomethane afforded 8-allyl-6,7-dimethoxyquinazolones XV and XVI.

fig. 3

XI : R = OMe;	R ₁ = H;	R ₂ = O allyl;	R ₃ = Me
XII : R = H;	R ₁ = OMe;	R ₂ = O allyl;	R ₃ = Me
XIII : R = OMe;	R ₁ = H;	R ₂ = O allyl;	R ₃ = Ph
XIV : R = H;	R ₁ = OMe;	R ₂ = O allyl;	R ₃ = Ph
XV : R = allyl;	R ₁ = R ₂ = OMe;		R ₃ = Me
XVI : R = allyl;	R ₁ = R ₂ = OMe;		R ₃ = Ph
XVII : R = allyl;	R ₁ = OMe;	R ₂ = OH;	R ₃ = Me
XVIII : R = allyl;	R ₁ = OMe;	R ₂ = OH.	R ₃ = Ph

The identical chemical behaviour of the benzoxazin-4-ones VI and VII shows that the substituents at positions 6 and 8 have similar effect on the stability and reactivity of these compounds. Unlike above, the isolation of the bisamide instead of 4-quinazolone during the action of aniline on 6-acetoxy-7-methoxy-2-methyl-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (IX)³ and 6-benzoyloxy-7-methoxy-2-phenyl-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (X)⁴ having similar

3. S. K. P. Sinha and D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 925.

4. S. K. P. Sinha, *ibid.*, in press.

substituents at positions 2 and 3 clearly indicates that the course of reaction is governed by the nucleophilic potential of the nitrogen atom at position-1 and therefore it is the substituent at its para position-6 which deactivates the molecule, not to get it cyclised *in situ*. This leads us to conclude that, whereas, the substituent at position 7, being in conjugation with the carbonyl group activates the molecule. the substituent at position 6 deactivates it leading to the opening of the ring.

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.p.s were determined in open capillaries in H_2SO_4 bath and are uncorrected. Light petroleum used has the b.p. 60–80°.

4-*Allyloxy-3-methoxy-2-acetamidobenzoic acid* (III) : A mixture of I² (2.23 g.; 0.01 mole) and Ac_2O (20 ml.) was refluxed for 30 min. when most of the solid dissolved. Next day it was warmed, filtered hot from insoluble material and the filtrate poured over crushed ice. and vigorously agitated when a precipitate was obtained. It was collected, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to give III as colourless needles (1.85 g.; 70%), m.p. 113–114°. (Found : C, 58.6; H, 5.4; N, 5.0. $C_{13}H_{15}O_5N$ requires : C, 58.8; H, 5.6; N, 5.2%).

7-*Allyloxy-8-methoxy-2-methyl-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one* (VI) : I (2.23 g.: 0.01 mole) was refluxed with Ac_2O (10 ml.) for 0.5 hr. and left overnight when colourless needles separated out. It was chilled in an ice bath, filtered and washed with dry ether to yield VI (2 g.; 80%). The product was pure enough for use in the next step. A sample crystallised from dry ethyl acetate-light petroleum melted at 146–147°. (Found : C, 63.0; H, 5.4; N, 5.8. $C_{13}H_{13}O_4N$ requires : C, 63.1; H, 5.2; N, 5.6%).

7-*Allyloxy-6-methoxy-2-methyl-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one* (VII) : II¹ (2.23 g.; 0.01 mole) was heated with Ac_2O (7 ml.) for 0.5 hr. and left overnight. The colourless solid which separated on cooling was collected as in the previous case and crystallised from dry benzene-light petroleum to yield VII as colourless felted needles (1.5 g.; 60%), m.p. 101–102°. (Found : C, 62.9; H, 5.0; N, 5.4. $C_{13}H_{13}O_4N$ requires : C, 63.1; H, 5.2; N, 5.6%).

7-*Allyloxy-8-methoxy-2-phenyl-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one* (VIII) : The amino acid I² (2.23 g.; 0.01 mole) dissolved in dry pyridine (5 ml.) was treated with benzoyl chloride (1.4 ml.; 0.012 mole), warmed on steam bath for 1 hr. and left overnight. The reaction mixture was poured in ice water and the solid that separated was collected, washed with water, dried and crystallised from Ac_2O to furnish VIII as elongated needles (1.85 g.; 60%), m.p. and m.m.p. 185–186°. (Found : C, 70.0; H, 5.0; N, 4.4. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{15}O_4N$: C, 69.9; H, 4.8; N, 4.5%).

7-*Allyloxy-8-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one* (XI) : VI (2.37 g.; 0.01 molè) was refluxed with $PhNH_2$ (0.9 ml; 0.01 mole) in dry toluene (10 ml.) for 4 hr., the excess solvent (4 ml.) was distilled off and the solid which separated from the cooled concentrated solution was filtered and washed with benzene. Crystallisation from dilute ethanol yielded XI as colourless needles (1 g.; 60%), m.p. 148–149°. (Found : C, 71.0; H, 5.8; N, 8.4. $C_{19}H_{18}O_3N_2$ requires : C, 70.8; H, 5.6; N, 8.7%).

7-*Allyloxy-6-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one* (XII) : VII (2.37 g.; 0.01 mole) when refluxed with PhNH_2 (0.9 ml.; 0.01 mole) in dry toluene (10 ml.) for 4 hr. and worked up as in the previous case afforded a white solid. It was crystallised from dilute ethanol to furnish XII as colourless needles (2 g.; 62%), m.p. and m.m.p. 160° (lit.¹ m.p. $160\text{--}161^\circ$).

7-*Allyloxy-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one* (XIII) : A mixture of VIII (3 g.; 0.01 mole) and PhNH_2 (0.9 ml.; 0.01 mole) in dry toluene (10 ml.) was refluxed for 4 hr. and worked up as above to give a white solid which on crystallisation from ethanol yielded XIII as colourless needles (2 g.; 52%), m.p. $132\text{--}133^\circ$ (lit.² m.p. 129°), m.m.p. 132° . (Found : C, 75.4; H, 5.1; N, 7.5. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$: C, 75.0; H, 5.2; N, 7.3%).

8-*Allyl-6,7-dimethoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one* (XV) : A slurry in ether of XVII (1 g.), obtained on Claisen rearrangement of XII as reported¹, was treated with ethereal diazomethane (from 1 g. *N*-nitrosomethylurea) and kept overnight. The solvent was evaporated and the residue on crystallisation from dilute methanol gave XV as colourless flakes (0.7 g.; 66%), m.p. $224\text{--}225^\circ$. (Found : C, 71.6; H, 6.0; N, 8.5. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires : C, 71.4; H, 5.9; N, 8.3%).

8-*Allyl-6,7-dimethoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one* (XVI) : Excess of ethereal diazomethane (from 1 g. *N*-nitrosomethylurea) was added to an ethereal suspension of the hydroxyquinazolone (XVIII; 1 g.), obtained after Claisen rearrangement of XIV as reported¹ and worked up as in the previous case to give a white solid. It was crystallised from dilute ethanol to afford XVI as colourless rectangular prisms (0.5 g.; 45%), m.p. $181\text{--}182^\circ$. (Found : C, 75.2; H, 5.6; N, 7.2. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires : C, 75.4; H, 5.5; N, 7.0%).

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